

Automatic Verification of FaaS Architectures

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1 Introduction

Serverless computing approaches, such as Function-as-a-Service (FaaS), have received much attention in recent years. In this paper, we present our new Constraint Definition Language (CDL), which provides a way of expressing the high level functional and non-functional requirements of a FaaS architecture. The Architecture Verification Tool (AVT) is able to check that a FaaS architecture (expressed in the TOSCA[8] modelling language) conforms to a CDL specification. We have evaluated the AVT on a “Socially Assistive Robotic Solution for Ambient Assisted Living” developed by Engineering Ingegneria Informatica. SARA is a combined smart-home/robotics system providing health monitoring and assistance in daily living to the elderly at home. It is a complex, distributed system comprising home automation devices, wearable health monitors, and a humanoid robot, all communicating with a backend e-Health management system, and various AI related cloud services. Such an interactive system, dealing with such sensitive (health) data, in such an intrusive (i.e. domotic/wearable) fashion demands strong constraints on performance, security and privacy. Some of these constraints – e.g. on the storage location and sharing of medical data – are even enforced by law. SARA provides a rich testing ground for our AVT.

2 The Architecture Verification Tool

The Constraint Definition Language (CDL) [6] is a new specification language, which can be used to annotate TOSCA models with formal requirements. The language allows references to predicates defined in the TOSCA model and allow users to define non-TOSCA predicates (e.g. the pre and post conditions of a lambda function). The language is based on first-order logic and allows to express many functional and non-functional requirements including on performance, security and privacy. For further details of the language, please see [6].

The Architecture Verification Tool [6] (AVT) provides an automated solution for verifying that a given TOSCA model complies with the requirements specified in a given CDL specification. The three phases of the AVT are shown in Figure 1. First (in the *pre-processing* stage) the TOSCA model and CDL specification are translated into the language of *Answer Set Programming* (ASP) [4, 1]. The

translated ASP program is then solved using an off-the-shelf ASP solver [3, 2] and each of the computed solutions can then be *post-processed*, yielding an inconsistency between the TOSCA model and the CDL specification. ASP was chosen for two main reasons: (1) the availability of efficient solvers; and (2) the potential to use existing systems for learning ASP [5, 7] to learn CDL constraints from examples of valid/invalid TOSCA models, which we intend to pursue in future work.

Fig. 1: Overview of the Architecture Verification Tool.

Initial Experimental Results. We evaluated the AVT on a TOSCA model representing the SARA architecture. We used a CDL specification expressing a very simple constraint that all nodes of a particular type must be located in the same country (to avoid confidential medical data being shared between countries). We generated 5 compliant TOSCA models and 5 non-compliant TOSCA models (i.e. models which had nodes of this type in multiple countries). The AVT was able to correctly classify every model, with an average running time of 7.9s. In future work, we intend to evaluate the tool on larger, more realistic CDL specifications.

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